

The Influence of Work Flexibility on Employee Performance in The Kutambaru District Office

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Abstract

The purpose of this research is to determine and analyze the influence of work flexibility on employee performance in Kutambaru District Office Employees. This research was carried out at the Kutambaru District Office. The type of research is associative quantitative. The sample in this study was 15 employees of the Kutambaru District Office. The sampling technique in this research uses saturated samples so that the entire population will be a sample of 15 people. The research results show that work flexibility has a significant influence on employee performance as shown by the T-Statistic value of $2.361 > 1.753$ and the P value of $0.000 < 0.05$. This shows that improvements in Work Flexibility can improve the Performance of Kutambaru District Office Employees Kutambaru District Office

Keywords: Work Flexibility; Performance

INTRODUCTION

Achieving company goals is the main task of all company elements and company employees as a whole, and is responsible for all business activities, uninterrupted company work, and achieving the highest sales output for the company. As time progresses, companies will form mutually beneficial relationships (symbiotic mutualism). In the business management process, it cannot be separated from the strategy and risk management inherent in the management context (Pohan, 2021). A company as an organization has a goal, namely making a profit. Organizations can operate because of activities or activities carried out by employees within the organization (Jufrizen & Rahmadhani, 2020).

Performance is the result of an employee's work during a certain period compared to various possibilities, for example standards, targets or criteria that have been determined in advance and mutually agreed upon (Pranoto, 2019). Performance is the work result that can be achieved by a person or group of people in an organization, in accordance with their respective authority and responsibilities, in order to achieve the goals of the organization in question legally, without violating the law and in accordance with norms and ethics.

Efforts to improve employee performance will certainly have an impact on the company's progress. The company will be able to survive amidst very tight business competition. Companies need to pay attention to several components and performance aspects related to human resources. Internal problems can arise at any time because one employee has different desires, needs and expectations. Such different responsibilities and working hours often cause conflict between family and work.

Working with more flexible working hours allows employees to organize their daily routines. Being flexible at work can influence employees' feelings of comfort with their

work, so that employees can work more freely and optimally. Work flexibility can usually encourage employees to come up with creative ideas in carrying out their work activities and responsibilities without having to rely on instructions from superiors. Besides that, with flexible working hours, employees are generally more satisfied with their work. This is also supported by the era of globalization which has become a phenomenon which is currently greatly influencing the business and service manufacturing industry.

The Kutambaru District Office has a crucial role in providing population administration services in its area. As an agency responsible for services, the Kutambaru District Office is faced with complex challenges that can affect the performance of its employees. According to the author's initial observations through observations and interviews with several employees, the phenomenon that occurs at the Kutambaru District Office is the complexity of handling community problems related to population documents that occur in Kutambaru.

According to Carlson in (Siregar et al., 2021) flexibility is a formal policy established by resource management or informal arrangements related to flexibility in a company. Furthermore, Carlson defines schedule flexibility as flexible work arrangements, which means choosing a place and time to work, whether formal or informal, which facilitates employees' policies.

Work flexibility is often associated with the expansion of deregulation in work. Being flexible is defined as someone who has the ability to be different according to what is needed, this idea reflects the ability to remain able to operate in conditions that are always changing, whether these changes can be predicted or not (Wahyuni, 2014).

According to Carlson in (Siregar et al., 2021) there are 3 indicators of work flexibility, namely: time flexibility, timing flexibility, and place flexibility. From this explanation, it can be concluded that there are 3 indicators in looking at flexibility in work, consisting of: time flexibility which shows how flexibility can regulate one's own work time. Timing flexibility shows how flexible employees are in choosing working hours. Place flexibility shows how flexible employees are in choosing a place of work.

According to (Fahmi, 2017) Performance is the result of a process that is referred to and measured over a certain period of time based on previously established provisions or agreements. Meanwhile, according to (Mangkunegara, 2016) employee performance is the achievement of employee work results based on quality and quantity as work performance within a certain period of time which is adjusted to the duties and responsibilities of a group within the organization in carrying out basic tasks and functions that are guided by norms, standard operating procedures, criteria and measures that have been established or are applicable in the organization.

To measure the level of employee performance in this research the author refers to theory (Fahmi, 2017), namely:

- 1) Quality, namely the level of errors, damage, accuracy.
- 2) Quantity, namely the number of jobs produced.
- 3) Use of time at work, namely the level of absenteeism, tardiness, effective working time/lost working hours.

4) Cooperate with other people at work.

The purpose of this research is to analyze and determine the effect of work flexibility on the performance of Kutambaru District Office Employees. The concept of this research is as depicted in the following conceptual framework image:

Figure 1. Conceptual Framework

METHOD

This type of research is casual associative quantitative research. This research was carried out at the Kutambaru District Office located at Jl. Community Health Center, Lau Lujur, Salapian, Kab. Langkat, North Sumatra, 20773. This research was carried out from March to April 2024. According to (Sugiyono, 2018b) population is a generalized area consisting of objects/subjects that have certain qualities and characteristics determined by the researcher to be studied and then conclusions are drawn. In this study, the population used was the entire number of employees at the Kutambaru District Office, totaling 15 people

The sampling technique used in this research was a saturated sample. According to (Sugiyono, 2018b) Saturated sampling is a sample selection technique if all members of the population are sampled, where the entire population in this study is sampled, namely 15 employees.

The data that will be used from this research is the data from the questionnaire distributed to respondents consisting of all employees in all divisions. The data analysis technique used in this research is a quantitative data analysis method using SPSS version 25.0.

Validity and reliability tests were carried out in order to test the quality of the research data. The validity test decision making criteria are as follows: If $r_{count} > r_{table}$, then the question item is valid. If $r_{count} < r_{table}$, then the question item is invalid. Meanwhile, the reliability test criteria are formulated if $r_{alpha} > r_{table}$ then the statement is reliable and if $r_{alpha} < r_{table}$ then the statement is not reliable.

The linear regression model was formulated in this research with the following formula:

$$Y = a + bX$$

Where :

Y = Employee Performance

X = Work Flexibility

a = Constant

b = Regression coefficient

The t-test in this research was carried out to determine the significance of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013). According to (Kuncoro & Hardani, 2013) the determination test (R^2) is used to measure how much influence the independent variable has on the dependent variable. In other words, the coefficient of determination is used to assess the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable studied, namely Work Flexibility (X), on the dependent variable, namely employee performance (Y). The coefficient of determination (R^2) value ranges from zero to one ($0 < R^2 < 1$) which means, if $R^2 = 0$, then there is no influence between variable (X) and variable (Y). Conversely, if R^2 approaches 1, then the influence between variable (X) and variable (Y) becomes stronger. Testing of the coefficient of determination was carried out using SPSS version 25.0 software.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Contents Results and Discussion

1. Research result

a) Descriptive Analysis

Descriptive Analysis This test is used to determine the minimum and maximum scores, the highest score, the rating score and the standard deviation of each variable. The results are as follows:

Table 1. Descriptive Statistics

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Work Flexibility	15	2.00	5.00	4.2213	,69777
Performance	15	3.00	5.00	4,1500	,51582
Valid N (listwise)	15				

The table above shows that the measurement results show that respondents assess that work flexibility and employee performance at the Kutambaru Subdistrict Office are above average, with mean values of 4,221 and 4,150 respectively on a scale of 1-5. The variation in respondents' assessments of these two variables is quite moderate, with almost the same standard deviation (0.697 for Work Flexibility and 0.515 for employee performance), indicating that although there are individual differences in perception, the majority of respondents have quite positive views of these two variables.

b) Validity and Reliability Test Results

Validity Test Results

The validity test is used to measure whether a questionnaire is valid or not. Validity testing carried out in this research was through the Corrected Item-Total Correlation test or better known as Person Correlation.

Table 2. Validity Test Results of the Work Flexibility Variable (X)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
FK1	0.784 > 0.514	0.001 < 0.05	Valid

FK2	0.755 > 0.514	0.001 < 0.05	Valid
FK3	0.862 > 0.514	0.000 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that the indicators for the Work Flexibility variable have a correlation coefficient value of > 0.514 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the indicators for the Work Flexibility variable are valid, (Sugiyono, 2018a).

Table 3. Validity Test Results for Employee Performance Variables (Y)

Variable	Correlation Value	Probability	Information
KIN1	0.767 > 0.514	0.001 < 0.05	Valid
KIN2	0.638 > 0.514	0.010 < 0.05	Valid
KIN3	0.829 > 0.514	0.000 < 0.05	Valid
KIN4	0.765 > 0.514	0.001 < 0.05	Valid

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25

From the data above it can be stated that all indicators on the employee performance variable have a correlation coefficient value greater than 0.514 with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$ so it can be concluded that the statements for the employee performance variable are valid, (Sugiyono, 2018a).

Reliability Test Results

According to (Ghozali, 2018) the reliability test aims to measure how reliable or reliable the questionnaire distributed to respondents is, which is useful as an instrument in this research. The reliability measurement method used in this research is by looking at the Cronbach Alpha (α) value. The questionnaire is declared reliable if the Cronbach Alpha (α) value is > 0.61 .

Table 4. Reliability Test Results

Variable	Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
Work Flexibility	0.721	3
Employee Performance	0.743	4

Source: Processed with SPSS version 25.0

Based on table 5, it is known that the Cronbach Alpha (α) value of the Work Flexibility and employee performance variables is greater than 0.60. So it can be concluded that all indicators in the variable instrument are declared reliable or reliable so that they can proceed to research hypothesis testing

c) Quantitative Analysis

This analysis is intended to determine the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable. The test results are as follows:

Simple Linear Regression Analysis

This regression test is intended to determine changes in the dependent variable if the independent variable experiences changes. The test results are as follows:

Table 5. Simple Linear Regression Test Results

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
	Coefficients		Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	8,839	,872		4,402	,001
Work Flexibility	,574	,204	,100	2,361	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the regression equation $Y = 8.839 + 0.574X$ is obtained. This equation is explained as follows: 1) A constant of 8.839 means that if there is no work flexibility, then there is an employee performance of 8.839 points. The Work Flexibility regression coefficient is 0.574, meaning that Work Flexibility influences an increase in employee performance by 0.574 for every 1 point increase.

Analysis of the Coefficient of Determination

To determine the magnitude of the influence of the independent variable on the dependent variable, a coefficient of determination analysis was carried out. The test results are as follows:

Table 6. Coefficient of Determination Test Results

Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate
1	,100a	,010	,166	,53263

a. Predictors: (Constant), Job Flexibility

The test results in table 7 show that the Adjusted R Square value is 0.166 or 16.60%, which means that work flexibility has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 83.40% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied.

t Test Results (Hypothesis Test)

Hypothesis testing with the t test is used to determine whether or not there is an influence of the dependent variable on the independent variable with the following hypothesis formulation:

Ho: There is no influence of Work Flexibility on employee performance at the Kutambaru District Head Office

Ha: There is an influence of work flexibility on employee performance at the Kutambaru District Head Office

The following are the results of the hypothesis test as shown in the following table:

Table 7. Hypothesis Test Results

Model	Unstandardized		Standardized	t	Sig.
	Coefficients		Coefficients		
	B	Std. Error	Beta		
1 (Constant)	8,839	,872		4,402	,001
Work Flexibility	,574	,204	,100	2,361	,000

a. Dependent Variable: Performance

Based on the test results in table 8, the calculated t value is $2.361 > t$ table 1.753, with a significance value of $0.000 < 0.05$, thus it can be stated that H_0 is rejected and H_a is accepted or that there is a positive and significant influence between Work Flexibility on employee performance at the Kutambaru District Head Office. .

Contents of Discussion Results

The findings in this research can be strengthened by referring to relevant previous research findings. In the context of the influence of Work Flexibility on the Performance of Kutambaru District Office Employees, this finding is in line with research results (Ariko, 2017) which show that the relationship between the work flexibility variable and employee performance has a calculated t value of 5.991 and a significance of 0.024, because the t value is $0.024 < (more\ small\ than)\ a = 0.05$, which means that work flexibility has a positive and significant effect on employee performance. The results of this research are in line with research (Altindag & Siller, 2014) in the context of the Effect of Flexible Working on Employee Performance An Empirical Study in Turkey. Shows that work flexibility has a positive and significant influence on employee performance. This means that improvements in work flexibility can contribute to improving the performance of Kutambaru District Office employees.

CLOSING

Conclusion

From the results of data analysis resulting from the research and discussion described above, it can be concluded that work flexibility (interpersonal relationships) does not have a significant influence on the performance of Kutambaru District Office Employees in the Kutambaru District Office with a calculated t value of $2.361 > t$ table 1.753, with a significance value $0.000 < 0.05$.

The adjusted R Square value is 0.166 or 16.60%, which means that work flexibility has a low influence on employee performance, while the remaining 83.40% is influenced by other factors that have not been studied. These results indicate that if work flexibility is increased, employee performance will tend to increase.

Suggestions and Acknowledgments

Based on the results of the research, discussion and conclusions obtained, suggestions that can be given are that the Work Flexibility and Performance variables need to be maintained and improved. Therefore, Kutambaru District Office Leaders should create an Organizational Culture that further improves interpersonal relationships with employees. Providing space for positive opinions for employees will also improve employee performance.

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